

The Phenomenon of Academic Procrastination in Students during Pandemic

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ABSTRACT: Pandemic becomes one of the problems of the world until the moment of this. In the aspect of education, the pandemic has changed the education system into online learning. We examine how the phenomenon of academic procrastination in online learning is due to previous research saying that the ineffectiveness of online learning causes students to do academic procrastination. A total of 305 students of the faculty of teacher training and science education fill out questionnaires online regarding the phenomenon of academic procrastination. The result of this research is that there are low and high comparisons on academic procrastination. The implications and discussion we discuss in depth.

KEYWORDS: Academic Procrastination, Students, Pandemic, COVID-19, Online Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Until August 4, 2021, based on data obtained from the WHO Coronavirus (COVID-19) Dashboard, COVID-19 cases continue to grow and reach 198,778,175 globally (World Health Organization, 2021). It is still growing every day. In Indonesia until August 4, 2021, crowd restrictions still apply because more and more cases are found. So that the impact is still ongoing, not least in the learning process. Online learning is a solution in dealing with crowd activity restrictions in schools and colleges. However, several studies have reported that online learning is ineffective (Dewantara & Nurgiansah, 2020; Nurdin & Anhusadar, 2020). Besides being ineffective, online learning has an impact on students (Handoyo et al., 2020) as well as on teachers (Anita et al., 2021)

Online learning is not new because it has been done long before the pandemic. However, online learning has become a "trend" when face-to-face learning is challenging to do during a pandemic. The implementation of online learning is enough to give a "culture shock" to teachers and students. This is due to the unpreparedness of the school in applying it. We reviewed several studies on the effectiveness of online learning, including reports of repeated boredom, incomprehensible material, and low ability to use technology (Dewantara & Nurgiansah, 2020). The results of another study found the main obstacles faced by students during online learning, including those related to the quality of Wi-Fi, the difficulty of finding a quiet space, financial problems, decreased social relations with peers, and healthy habits (Gonzalez-Ramirez et al., 2021). Supported by other studies which say that online classes are of poor quality, lack of interest and motivation of students to attend classes, uncomfortable using online channels, technical barriers such as poor network connectivity, power outages, poor audio and video. In addition, they find it difficult to concentrate during online classes; there are many distractions at home, there is no structured learning environment that makes it harder for students to focus during class (Nambiar, 2020). even recent research says that online learning has an impact on unethical behaviour (Herdian et al., 2021).

Other research focuses on the impact felt by students, namely the occurrence of academic procrastination. This is because they do not understand the material presented by the teacher, are not confident in their abilities, cannot manage time to do assignments with other activities, students feel bored and bored because of online learning at home, lack of attention and motivation to learn from parents, and obstacles. Signal, cellphone, and internet quota (Wulandari et al., 2021) The problem of the emergence of procrastination behavior is reinforced by Handoyo et al. (2020), who found high procrastination in students when learning online. The report on the research results by Haryanti & Santoso (2020) regarding academic forecasting in students, as many as 74% of students are in the medium category. As many as 13.4% of students are in the high category. Forms of procrastination by students include; delaying assignments in the hope of getting a lot of time to complete academic assignments, lecturers gave assignments that are too difficult, difficult to find materials, difficult to get a wifi signal, boring teaching methods, poor time management, paying attention to other things, and helping parents at home (Turmudi & Suryadi, 2021).

Referring to the definition, procrastination is a tendency to delay starting or completing other useless activities so that performance becomes hampered, never completes tasks on time, and is often late in attending meetings (Solomon & Rothblum,

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1984). In addition, the definition of academic procrastination is a delay made on formal tasks related to academic tasks, such as school assignments or coursework (Ferrari et al., 1995)

Many factors cause procrastination behavior to emerge. Generally caused by physical, psychological, and environmental factors (Fauziah, 2015). Surijah & Tjundjing, (2007) say that procrastination factors include the level of aversiveness of a task, orientation to time, perfectionism, age and gender, natural conditions, psychological conditions, and physiological conditions. Previous research has reported that academic procrastination is related to personality, namely in aspects of low awareness (competence, orderliness, devotion, struggle for achievement, self-discipline, deliberation) and aspects of neuroticism (anxiety, depression, self-awareness, impulsivity, vulnerability) (Watson, 2001). Recent research has also suggested that procrastination is caused by personality extraversion and neuroticism (Kim et al., 2017), is negatively associated with harmonious desires, and positively associated with obsessive desires (Peixoto et al., 2021). they are influencing self-efficacy. Significant negative effect on procrastination, while test anxiety has a significant positive effect on procrastination (Ariani & Susilo, 2018), external locus of control (Khoshouei, 2017). they are related to GPA and organizational activities (Jannah & Muis, 2014). Meanwhile, based on demographics, men have a higher average academic procrastination value than women's average academic procrastination score (Erdianto & Dewi, 2020).

Procrastination is a dangerous behavior, not only has a bad impact on students' academic performance and reduces the productivity of those who work. In addition, it prevents individuals from reaching their full potential, has a negative impact on their mental health, and is sometimes harmful to interpersonal relationships (Fernie et al., 2017). Based on this background, the purpose of our research is to examine how procrastination behavior occurs in students majoring in teacher training and education in higher education.

II. METHOD

The variable in this study is Academic Procrastination. While the research method uses a quantitative descriptive approach. This method is considered suitable to describe the behavior of academic procrastination with relatively many participants. The sample of this study was students of the faculty of teacher training and education at the Muhammadiyah University of Purwokerto. The number of samples for this study was 305 students from the teaching and education faculties from 9 study programs who were in the even semester level.

Table 1. Demographic Data

No	Criteria	N	%
1.	Sex		
	Male	56	18,4%
	Female	249	81,6%
2.	Study program		
	English Education Program	68	22,3%
	Indonesian education Program	53	17,4%
	biology education program	22	7,2%
	geography education program	5	1,6%
	mathematics education program	56	18,4%
	history education program	15	4,9%
	early childhood education program	15	4,9%
	elementary school teacher program	57	18,7%
Pancasila and civic education	14	4,6%	
3.	Semesters		
	2	28	9,2%
	4	73	23,9%
	6	127	41,6%
	8	75	24,6%
10	2	0,7%	
4	GPA		
	< 2,00	3	1,0%
	2,00 – 2,75	2	0,7%
	2,76 – 3,50	159	52,1%
	3,51 – 4,00	141	46,2%

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Based on table 1. Profile of the study program obtained nine study programs. Most participants were obtained from Indonesian language education study programs as many as 68 people or 22.3%, elementary school teacher education study programs obtained as many as 57 people or 18.7%, mathematics education study programs as many as 56 people or 18.4%, study programs English language and literature education obtained as many as 53 people or 17.4%, biology education study program obtained as many as 22 people or 7.2%, history education study program obtained as many as 15 people or 4.9%, PG-PAUD study program obtained as many as 15 people or 4.9%, the PPKn study program obtained as many as 14 people or 4.6%, the geography education study program obtained as many as five people or 1.6%.

Two hundred forty-nine female participants with 81.6% dominated the categorization of participants based on gender in this study. In contrast, the male participants were 56 people with a percentage of 18.4%. The profile of participants per semester is divided into five categories. The 6th-semester participants were the most participants, with a total of 127 people or 41.6%. There were 75 people in the 8th semester or 24.6%, the 4th semester as many as 73 people or 23.9%, the 2nd semester as many as 9.2%, and two people in the 10th semester or 0.7%. Researchers divided the GPA ranges into four. The highest GPA range is 3.51 - 4.00, while the lowest range is <2.00. This study was dominated by participants with a GPA range of 2.76 - 3.50, amounting to 159 people or 52.1%. Participants with a GPA range of 3.51 - 4.00 totaling 141 people or 46.2%. Participants with a GPA range of 2.00 - 2.75 totaling three people or 1.0%, and minimum participants in the range <2.00 with a total of 2 people or 0.7%.

We are collecting data using a procrastination academic scale-student measuring instrument. This scale is based on the indicators of Academic Procrastination proposed by Solomon & Rothblum, (1984), including: being late in doing writing assignments, delaying studying when facing exams, postponing reading activities, delaying administrative task performance, delaying to attend face-to-face, postponement of overall academic performance.

This scale is divided into two parts, the first part is the prevalence of academic procrastination in 6 areas, and the second part is the reasons for academic procrastination. An example item in part 1 is "To what extent is delaying writing a paper/report a problem for you?" and in part 2, "I have many other things to do". Scoring data using a Likert scale on part 1 of 1 (Never) to 5 (always), then on part 2 of 1 (Strongly disagree) to 5 (Strongly agree). This scale is a favored statement, with a total of 32 items. The academic-student procrastination scale has a reliability = 0.854.

Based on the results of the analysis of the Procrastination Academic Scale-Student trial, it was found that a valid item has a validity coefficient of 0.021 to 0.633. The results of the validity test carried out on 44 items are 12 invalid items and 32 valid items, the items that fall are caused by the validity coefficient, which is 0.30, then it must be aborted. Data analysis uses quantitative analysis by categorizing and making percentages, while statistical analysis uses SPSS statistical program assistance.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Informant 1 said that in the control aspect, he often advised children and carried out direct and indirect supervision. Informant 1 also felt a little difficulty in controlling the child because he felt tired of advising children who only answered yes but did not necessarily do it and the dilemma between the behavior that was carried out was often contrary to the heart because he did not have the heart. In Informant 2, the control aspect of children dressed neatly and teaching manners was then asked to study religion by reciting the Koran, the informant was also fairly strict in looking after children when going to play or studying groups must be picked up if the distance was far In Informant 3, the control aspect that arises is the supervision of children while playing by looking for children's playgrounds where, to control their own children, sometimes punishments such as hitting children. For Informants 4, the control aspect is by giving the advice to be more independent and teaching manners as initial behavior control. Meanwhile, the difficulty felt by informant 4 was that it was difficult for children to obey orders. Therefore, informant 4 gave a gift/reward to the child if he could do what the parents asked him to do, this was one of the informants' ways to control the child, besides that there was a reduction in pocket money if he could not do it according to the agreement. Informant 4 also sometimes threatened children to report to their father if the child did not obey.

Below are the results of data collection obtained by researchers, then the characteristics of respondents for Academic Procrastination are as follows:

Table 2. Frequency Distribution of Academic Procrastination Score

Category	Score Range	Frequency	Percent
Very low	$X < 73,90$	10	3,3%
Low	$73,90 < X \leq 90,57$	66	21,6%
Moderate	$90,57 < X \leq 107,25$	150	49,2%
High	$107,25 < X \leq 123,93$	68	22,3%
Very high	$X > 123,93$	11	3,6%
Total		305	100

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Based on table 2. above, it can be seen that the categories in the percentage of subject answers, namely 11 people (3.6%), stated that they had very high academic procrastination, 68 people (22.3%) stated that they had high academic procrastination, 150 people (49, 2%) stated that they had moderate academic procrastination, 66 people (21.6%) said they had low academic procrastination, ten people (3.3%) said they had very low academic procrastination. When compared with low (including very low) and high (including very high) frequencies, 76 low frequencies and 79 high frequencies are obtained. The comparison value does not show a significant difference. However, the difference is the difference between the two frequencies. While the results of the highest frequency in the medium category. So it can be concluded that overall academic procrastination (scale part 1 and part 2) is dominated by the moderate category.

Table 3. Frequency Distribution of Academic Procrastination Scale Part 1 (prevalence of academic procrastination)

Category	Score Range	Frequency	Percent
Very low	$X < 21,35$	7	2,3%
Low	$21,35 < X \leq 29,75$	64	21,0%
Moderate	$29,75 < X \leq 38,15$	139	45,6%
High	$38,15 < X \leq 46,55$	83	27,3%
Very high	$X > 46,55$	12	3,9%
Total		305	100

Based on table 3. the frequency distribution of part 1 of the academic procrastination scale is known to be the category in the percentage of the subject's answers, namely 12 people (3.9%) stated that they had very high academic procrastination, 83 people (27.3%) stated that they had high academic procrastination, 139 people (45.6%) said they had moderate academic procrastination, 64 people (21%) said they had low academic procrastination, seven people (2.3%) said they had very low academic procrastination. Compared with low (including very low) and high (including very high) frequencies, the low frequencies are 71, and the high is 95. The comparison value shows a significant difference. The difference is a difference of 24 frequencies. While the results of the highest frequency in the medium category. So it can be concluded that overall academic procrastination (part 1 scale) is dominated in the moderate category.

Table 4. Frequency Distribution of Academic Procrastination Scale Part 2 (the reasons for academic procrastination)

Category	Score Range	Frequency	Percent
Very low	$X < 46,32$	12	3,9%
Low	$46,32 < X \leq 58,75$	51	16,7%
Moderate	$58,75 < X \leq 71,14$	161	52,8%
High	$71,14 < X \leq 83,52$	70	23,0%
Very high	$X > 83,52$	11	3,6%
Total		305	100

Based on table 4. The distribution of the frequency of the academic procrastination scale part 2, which is the reason for procrastination, it is known that the category in the percentage of the subject's answers, namely 11 people (3.6%), stated that they had very high reasons for academic procrastination, 70 people (23%) stated that they had procrastination reasons. High academic achievement, 161 people (52.8%) stated that they had moderate academic procrastination reasons, 51 people (16.7%) stated that they had low academic procrastination reasons, 12 people (3.9%) stated that they had moderate academic procrastination reasons. Very low. Compared with low (including very low) and high (including very high) frequencies, the low frequencies are 63, and the high is 81. The comparison value shows a significant difference. The difference is 18 frequencies. While the results of the highest frequency in the medium category. So it can be concluded that overall academic procrastination (part 2) is dominated in the moderate category.

In table 5. The prevalence of results based on responses is shown. We only highlight a high percentage of "never/ rarely" and "often/ always" responses. The results obtained on the Procrastinating to do reading assignments dimension, on the item "To what extent would you like to reduce your tendency to procrastinate reading assigned material?" have a higher percentage of often (30.2) and always (50.8) in response choices. This shows that there is a desire to reduce delays in reading the material. However, this is not matched by how it should be done. So it can be concluded that there is "laziness" in reading the material obtained from lectures. Table 5. It also shows the results on the Procrastinating to do academic, administrative tasks dimension, on the item "To what extent have you delayed completing this academic administration?" had a "never" response percentage of 40.7% and rarely as much as 33.8%. This is not much different from the item "To what extent has the delay in academic administration tasks been a problem for you?" with the percentage of response "never" as much as 26.6% and rarely as much as 41.0%. This shows that

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students do not do many academic delays related to administration. Maybe this is considered relatively easy to do than doing other tasks that require quite a lot of energy in thinking.

Table 5. Academic procrastination based on item responses on a scale of part 1 (prevalence of academic procrastination)

Procrastination area	Aitem	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
Procrastination in writing a paper or report	How often do you put off writing an assigned paper/report?	2.6	18.7	50.8	19.7	8.2
	To what extent has the delay in writing a paper/report a problem for you?	4.9	39.7	22.6	26.9	5.9
Procrastination in studying for exams	How often do you put off studying for exams?	9.2	21.0	43.9	17.4	8.5
	To what extent has delaying studying for exams been a problem for you?	6.6	30.2	26.2	26.9	10.2
Procrastinating to do reading assignments	How often do you procrastinate reading assigned material?	3.0	22.0	40.7	25.2	9.2
	To what extent is delaying reading assigned material a problem for you?	5.2	34.4	28.9	26.2	5.2
	To what extent you would like to reduce your tendency to procrastinate reading assigned material?	3.3	3.3	12.5	30.2	50.8
Procrastinating to do academic, administrative tasks	To what extent have you delayed completing this academic administration?	40.7	33.8	16.1	5.6	3.9
	To what extent has the delay in academic administration tasks been a problem for you?	26.6	41.0	12.1	13.8	6.6
Procrastinating academic attendance assignments	To what extent is this delay in attendance a problem for you?	27.2	34.4	13.1	14.1	11.1
Procrastinating to carry out campus activities in general	To what extent have you delayed participating in activities on this campus?	19.7	43.3	23.9	11.1	2.0
	To what extent is delaying participating in campus activities a problem for you?	16.4	44.9	13.1	19.0	6.6

Note: the one marked in yellow has the highest percentage and is discussed

Table 6. The results show that there are several reasons for academic procrastination. Among them are worried that cause students to procrastinate, such as worrying about assignments that lecturers don't like, not meeting their expectations, bad grades, and not meeting standards. In addition, there is discomfort or courage in asking the lecturer, lots of freedom so that they are overwhelmed, following friends who have not done assignments, dislikes task deadlines, and low motivation in working on papers.

Table 6. Academic procrastination based on item responses on a part 2 (the reasons for academic procrastination)

Reasons for Academic Procrastination	Prevalence (%), n = 305				
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree or disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
I'm worried that my lecturer doesn't like my assignment	20	39.34	31.47	7.54	1.64
I have a hard time deciding what to write and not to write in my paper assignments/reports	11.14	29.5	36.4	20.65	2.3
I have a question about additional information that I need, but I am not comfortable asking my lecturer	12.78	34.42	26.88	22.3	3.6
I'm worried about getting bad grades	39.01	39.34	14.09	6.23	1.31
I don't like being assigned tasks by other	7.54	17.05	50.5	23.6	1.31

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people					
I think I don't quite understand how to write a paper/report	5.24	13.11	29.5	46.88	5.24
I don't like writing papers	5.9	13.44	44.91	28.52	7.21
I am overwhelmed with tasks	14.75	27.21	35.4	18.68	3.93
I have a hard time asking for information from other people	4.6	13.77	33.44	40.99	7.21
I'm eagerly waiting for the last minute assignment	7.54	18.68	33.77	28.52	11.47
I can't choose some of the topics to work on	2.95	14.09	43.27	34.09	5.57
I don't have enough energy to start working on tasks	2.62	16.72	26.88	41.96	11.8
I feel like I need a lot of time to do my paper	16.72	45.9	28.85	7.21	1.31
I like the challenge of waiting until the time limit	9.83	26.23	28.85	25.57	9.5
I know that my friend hasn't started working on the assignment either	10.49	44.26	33.11	9.83	2.3
I don't like other people setting a time limit for me	16.06	33.44	34.75	13.77	1.96
I'm worried that I can't live up to my expectations	21.31	47.86	19.01	9.83	3.93
I'm worried that if I get good grades, other people will have high expectations of me in the future	17.7	37.04	28.52	12.78	3.93
I have high standards, and I'm worried that I won't be able to meet them	18.03	34.75	29.83	34.75	1.31
I just feel too lazy to do the paper	18.36	32.45	30.16	14.42	4.6

Note: the one marked in yellow has the highest percentage and is discussed

The results of this study provide information on academic procrastination during the pandemic. The results show that procrastination occurs due to student reasons. The results in part 1 and part 2 show the high academic procrastination of students. This is in line with the results of previous research, which said that online learning, which was used as a learning solution during a pandemic, triggered the emergence of academic procrastination (Handoyo et al., 2020). In addition, other studies also explain the reasons or causes of academic procrastination, including not being confident in their abilities (Wulandari et al., 2021). In addition, anxiety or worry about students' self-obsessive desires may not meet self-standards or expectations (Peixoto et al., 2021). This research contributes to universities providing treatment so that academic dishonesty behavior does not continue in students. In addition, it should be noted that the learning design is not saturated, and the task load is not too much so that students can follow the lesson well.

IV. CONCLUSION

We examine the behavior of academic procrastination in teaching and educating students during a pandemic. The high behavior of academic procrastination causes students not to be able to receive lessons properly. So universities need to deal with this problem. The reasons for academic procrastination in this study illustrate that students do not procrastinate only in several aspects. What is quite a concern is that students do not procrastinate only in the administrative aspect. While on reading assignments, students do academic procrastination. Worry is the most common reason for academic dishonesty behavior. So there is a need for a study of stress in students who experience academic procrastination.

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